

Methodology of Spiritual Education in Primary Education

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Abstract: reforms in the education system make the use of information technologies relevant for primary school students. From this point of view, in the article we tried to highlight the problems of spiritual education of primary school students.

Keywords: spirituality, information technologies, education, improvement of education.

INTRODUCTION

After our country gained independence, serious attention was paid to environmental education of the third generation. At the heart of it, the goal of protecting the ecology of our state and stabilizing relations with the environment was set at a high level. In this regard, the following words of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh.M. Mirziyev, are noteworthy: "The most important issue is to raise the ecological culture of the population." Of course, such problems cannot be solved only by administrative means, it can be achieved by instilling in the hearts of the next generation love for mother nature, a sense of belonging to her.

Before implementing ecological education, if we analyze the word ecology, it means "roof" or "house". Ecology was introduced to science for the first time by the German scientist

Ernest Haeckel. Ecological science has many branches in the modern era of market relations: plant ecology, zoology, soil ecology, human ecology, etc. Ecological education is the formation of a correct, rational attitude towards nature in a person works on the issue and sets the goal of forming environmental culture in students. In 2017/2021, to implement the tasks defined in the Strategy of Actions on the five priority areas of the development of the Republic of

Uzbekistan, to contribute to the solution of environmental problems in the territories of the Republic by introducing the educational system, while following the following: Increasing the environmental literacy of the growing generation; Formation and development of ecological awareness and ecological culture; It is created in order to effectively organize the process of ecological education and upbringing. Decision No. 434 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of

Uzbekistan "On approval of the concept of development of environmental education in the Republic of Uzbekistan" was adopted. As an appendix to the decision, the Concept of Development of Ecological Education in the Republic of Uzbekistan was developed. The

main goal of the concept is the formation and development of ecological knowledge, consciousness and culture in the growing generation, effective organization of environmental education and training, as well as further improvement of science in the field of ecology, involving the world's advanced innovative technologies. In this concept, special emphasis is placed on the place and role of environmental education at all stages of education. The following priority tasks are defined in the department of improvement of environmental education in the general secondary education system

1.1. The state educational standard and curriculum of general secondary education will be reanalyzed based on the parameters of the formation of environmental culture in students, and additional indicators will be determined.

- The content of the state educational standard and curriculum of general secondary education will be enriched with the following qualifications:
- knowledge that serves to form environmental culture in students,
- extensive assimilation of skills and competencies into the content of
- education;
- putting ecological knowledge into practice within academic subjects, enriching it with practical tasks that allow them to be applied in practice (transition from theory or discussion to practice);

1.2. In the general secondary education system, environmental knowledge is organized on the basis of differentiation at the class level, taking into account the performance, physical capabilities and psychological characteristics of students. In this case, education should become a target system that ensures the gradual formation of environmental culture and education in students, relying on pedagogical principles such as "from simple to complex", "integrality and continuity", combining theoretical and practical knowledge.

1.3. In the general secondary education system, the knowledge, skills and competences aimed at the formation of ecological culture and the theoretical foundations of ecology are given on the basis of coherence in the content of existing academic subjects and are expressed in a comprehensive way. In this case, a person who has completed the general secondary education system will have a minimal level of knowledge about ecological concepts, rules of behavior (ecological culture), ecological knowledge will be inculcated in the content of the sciences, not as a compulsory measure, but based on the content of the science.

1.4. Environmental education is carried out in the general secondary education system at the following levels: Primary education (grades I-IV), General secondary education (grades V-IX). Primary education focuses on building the foundation of literacy, knowledge and skills necessary for environmental education.

1.5. In primary grades, students in the framework of educational subjects additionally:
Water saving and conservation; -The importance of atmospheric air and its protection;
- Rational use of land resources and underground resources; - Protection of flora and fauna; - Collection and disposal of waste; - To preserve the beautiful and unique nature of Uzbekistan; - Active participation in the preservation of the nature of the village (city) where he lives; About nature reserves and parks in

Uzbekistan; Must have general knowledge and skills about the tragedy of the Aral Sea.

1.6. In addition to the content of general secondary education subjects: a) to know and sing songs on the subject of the student's love for mother nature as parents;

b) to be able to observe and describe natural scenes in fine arts; being able to draw the

rarest and rarest species of plants and animals from the Red Book of the Republic of Uzbekistan;

C) Be able to understand the negative consequences of harming nature, including dumping waste in unspecified places;

e) strengthening the love between man and nature; Be able to describe scenes related to global environmental problems;

v) to the sciences of state and legal foundations: the provisions of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan on ecology and environmental protection; Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Nature Protection";

g) subjects related to the foundations of economic knowledge: the need to comply with environmental requirements in the implementation of entrepreneurial activities; existence of separate payment systems for environmental pollution;

d) sciences related to the basics of chemistry: atmospheric and ozone-depleting substances and their characteristics; negative impact of substances contained in waste on nature in the disposal of household and industrial waste;

j) to the sciences related to the basics of biology: rare and rare plant and animal species included in the Red Book of the Republic of Uzbekistan; The colorful fauna and flora of nature reserves and parks in Uzbekistan, their distribution areas; forests, their importance and conservation of forests;

z) Subjects, necessary knowledge and information about the description of protected natural areas are included in geography sciences.

1.7. Textbooks and study guides for general secondary education will be improved by infusing the knowledge of environmental culture into relevant topics. Specialists will develop teaching and demonstration materials, videos and didactic materials for general education schools in accordance with the needs of students on current problems such as environmental protection, drinking water and other natural resources. Subjects of environmental education are introduced in accordance with the content of science programs taught in general education schools.

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